
Non-Monetary Incentives and Staff Productivity in Private Healthcare Facilities in Anambra State, Nigeria

¹Njoku, Ifeanyi Michael, Ph.D. and ²Bello, Aisha Rahmat, Ph.D.

¹Department of Management Sciences, Faculty of Business Administration
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

²Department of Sociology and Behavioural Studies, Faculty of Social and Management Sciences
University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria

Abstract

This study explored the association between non-monetary incentives and employee productivity in selected private healthcare facilities located in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study specifically sought to: determine the relationship between employee recognition and level of work output, examine the effect of flexible work scheduling on employee responsiveness, and assess the link between assigning greater responsibility and employee retention. The research focused on six private hospitals within the study area. A descriptive survey research design was employed. Data were collected primarily through structured questionnaires administered to staff members. The total population comprised 683 employees across the selected hospitals. Using Cochran's sampling formula, a sample size of 246 respondents was obtained. Out of the distributed questionnaires, 242 were correctly completed and returned for analysis. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean scores, while Pearson correlation analysis was applied to test the study hypotheses. The results revealed that employee recognition had a positive and statistically significant relationship with output level ($r = .224$). Flexible work schedules were also found to have a positive relationship with employee responsiveness ($r = .468$). Furthermore, assigning employees greater responsibilities showed a positive association with staff retention ($r = .374$). Based on the findings, the study concluded that non-financial incentives contribute positively to employee performance within private healthcare institutions. Consequently, the study recommends that hospital management should adopt recognition practices as an important motivational strategy to enhance teamwork, commitment, and overall organizational effectiveness.

Keywords: Non-monetary incentives, employee productivity, recognition, flexible work schedule, employee retention

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19136429>

Introduction

All organizations strive for growth, sustainability, and improved performance in an increasingly competitive environment. Modern organizations, regardless of their size or industry, continuously seek strategies to retain competent employees and maximize productivity. Building and sustaining positive relationships between employees and their organizations is therefore essential to achieving long-term success. Human resources represent the most valuable asset of any organization. Consequently, managers must adopt effective methods to motivate employees and encourage them to perform their responsibilities efficiently. Many organizations implement various strategies to motivate their workforce

in order to remain competitive and achieve organizational goals. One of the most widely recognized strategies is the use of reward systems that acknowledge employees' contributions and efforts (Kumar, Hossain, & Nasrin, 2017). Organizational policies, management practices, and welfare programs significantly influence employee performance. When employees operate within supportive and well-structured work environments, they tend to perform their duties more effectively. Reward systems play a crucial role in strengthening employee commitment and improving productivity. Studies have consistently demonstrated that properly designed incentive systems contribute positively to employee performance (Choudhary & Ghosh, 2017).

For organizations to maintain a competitive advantage, managers must ensure that employees remain motivated and committed to achieving organizational objectives. Motivation serves as a driving force that encourages workers to apply their skills and energy toward the accomplishment of assigned tasks. Employees who are well motivated typically demonstrate higher levels of dedication, creativity, and productivity. In recent years, organizations have increasingly recognized the importance of non-financial incentives in motivating employees. Unlike financial rewards, non-monetary incentives address employees' psychological, social, and emotional needs. Such incentives may include recognition, opportunities for career development, increased responsibilities, and flexible work arrangements. These forms of motivation can significantly influence employees' attitudes toward their jobs and enhance their overall performance (Priyanka & Sulakshna, 2021). Since individuals possess diverse needs that extend beyond financial compensation, organizations must adopt motivational strategies that cater to these broader needs. Non-financial rewards therefore serve as valuable tools for improving employee morale and performance. Against this background, this study examines the relationship between non-financial rewards and employee performance in private healthcare institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Non-financial incentives such as recognition, career advancement opportunities, increased job responsibilities, and professional appreciation often have a significant influence on employee motivation. In many situations, these incentives may even have a stronger motivational impact than monetary rewards alone. When employees feel valued and appreciated for their contributions, they tend to develop stronger commitment toward their organizations. Employees represent the human capital of any organization, and their motivation directly affects organizational productivity. Motivated employees usually demonstrate dedication, creativity, and persistence in performing their duties. In contrast, employees who lack motivation often exhibit poor work attitudes, reduced productivity, frequent absenteeism, and sometimes a desire to leave the organization for better opportunities.

Many employees in private healthcare institutions operate under demanding working conditions. They often encounter challenges such as inadequate recognition, rigid work schedules, and increased job responsibilities without adequate appreciation. These challenges sometimes lead to negative work attitudes, including lateness, absenteeism, reduced commitment to tasks, and prioritizing personal matters over professional responsibilities. Employee turnover has also become a persistent issue in many private hospitals, as skilled workers frequently leave one organization for similar roles in other institutions offering better working conditions. Such trends can negatively affect organizational performance by reducing productivity, increasing recruitment costs, and weakening staff morale.

The consequences of these challenges include declining productivity, reduced organizational efficiency, employee dissatisfaction, and high staff turnover. These issues have increasingly affected the reputation and performance of private healthcare institutions both locally and internationally. Given these challenges, it is important to examine how non-financial incentives influence employee performance in

private hospitals. Therefore, this study investigates the relationship between non-monetary reward systems and employee performance in private healthcare institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the relationship between Non financial reward and employee performance of private hospitals in Enugu State. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the relationship between recognition and the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between flexible working hours and employee responsiveness of private hospitals in Enugu State.
- iii. Determine the relationship between employee with more responsibility and retention of private hospitals in Enugu State.

Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between recognition and the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the relationship between flexible working hours and employee responsiveness of private hospitals in Enugu State?
- iii. What is the relationship between employee with more responsibility and retention of private hospitals in Enugu state?

Statement of Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null Hypotheses.

- i. Recognition has no positive significant relationship with the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State.
- ii. Flexible working hours have no positive significant relationship with employee responsiveness of private hospitals in Enugu State.
- iii. Employee with more responsibility has no positive significant relationship with retention of private hospitals in Enugu State.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Non-Financial

This phrase is used when referring to or not being about finances. Non-financial considerations are those that can influence a financial choice and ought to be put into consideration at all times. Non-financial metrics, which can be both qualitative and quantitative, cannot be expressed in monetary terms. Typically, these metrics aid in determining the caliber of the goods or services a business provides (Cornish, 2018).

Reward

Generally speaking, reward refers to the overall monetary and non-monetary compensation or payment given to an employee in exchange for labor or services supplied at work. Perhaps the most important contract element in every paid-work arrangement is reward, often known as pay or remuneration (Joycelyn, Amewugah & Mawutor, 2018). An employee's performance may be improved through reward, which has a good motivating effect. It is possible to say that all of the measures done by the company to raise employee performance are incentives.

Non-Monetary Reward

Although money can play a significant role in a person's decision to work or in their performance, other rewards are frequently more significant when it comes to motivating them at work. Non-financial awards

are those that do not count toward an employee's compensation. They are tangible or observable incentives used in organizations to motivate employees in the absence of direct monetary pay. Physical items such as citations, gifts, certifications, apparel, key holders, and reduced tickets to use various office amenities are examples of perceptible, non-financial reasons. The idea that money is a powerful incentive may sound reasonable, yet many individuals really do not view money as the most important motivator at all. According to Wiesen (2019), non-financial incentives have the potential to motivate employees who do not get monetary compensation. Non-financial rewards for work-related activities may naturally motivate employees. Jobs with a variety of responsibilities, accountability, independence, empowerment, and career development opportunities are crucial in meeting employees' individual needs and may lead to a situation where the employee feels that the work is noteworthy of putting in more effort without the need for any outside compensation. Organizations utilize a variety of non-cash rewards to encourage employees, including praise, training opportunities, job promotions, and opportunities for career development (Agbenyegah, 2019).

Non-financial reward components employed to achieve study goals.

Acknowledgement

Recognition is the expression of admiration and thanks. The idea behind positive reinforcement is that behaviors and actions that result in rewards are more likely to occur again and again. Employees who are acknowledged therefore feel motivated to improve their performance. A status system is an essential motivational tool inside a company. Because of this, the competence, abilities, and talents of employees in firms should serve as the foundation for recognition programs (Wambugu & Ombui, 2018). Both material and intangible things can be used to recognize employees. It is often characterized by appreciation programs (oral and non-oral), enabling employees to participate in decision-making, devolution of authority, financial incentives, certificates of appreciation, and recognition ceremonies, among other things (Wambugu & Ombui, 2018). Managers who understand that high-performing staff are more difficult to retain typically utilize recognition and incentive programs to drive their businesses to success. There are two types of reward programs: official and unauthorized. Wairimu and Ndeto (2019) note that the use of prizes as a motivational technique boosts staff morale, decreases stress and absenteeism, and further lowers employee turnover. As a result, reward programs not only benefit employees, but also the employer, who enjoys lower turnover costs and higher employee productivity.

Flexible Working Hours

The term "flexible work hours" refers to a practice where businesses permit employees to change their start and end times from the typical 9 am to 5 pm (Indeed Editorial Team, 2021). The entire daily work schedule of such an employee nevertheless satisfies the requisite working hours set forth in the parties' agreement notwithstanding the change in scheduling. In other words, these workers continue to put in a set number of hours, and they continue to be held accountable for achieving their goals. Flexible schedules or "flex-time" are other terms for flexible working hours. Millennials are drawn to the idea, and the motivations behind this are not implausible (Jobberman, 2019).

More Responsibilities for the Employee

Employers choose employees based on their capacity to carry out the obligations listed in a formal job description. The job description specifies the duties and responsibilities of each employee and states explicitly what skills and expectations the employer has. Work responsibility is defined as the performance of all work tasks as outlined in the job description and the professional and best-effort adherence to corporate policies and procedures. Being accountable at work demonstrates your worth as an employee and your dependability to your colleagues. The degree to which you are responsible at work

depends on your everyday activities, your conduct during special work-related events, and how you treat other employees. Your employment environment and particular function will determine the kinds of duties you have and the standards expected of your behavior there (James, 2019).

Personnel

An employee is just someone who works for someone else who directs what has to be done and how it is done (Ian, 2021). An employee is a person who companies recruit and pay for the work they perform. Employees are defined as those who follow the instructions of other firm specialists. Employers have some degree of influence over the actions, money, and perks of their employees. Employers pay employees to carry out certain jobs and obligations for them. They frequently have full-time, part-time, or temporary employment. Employees carry out certain duties and obligations that are frequently outlined in the job description. Based on their entire work experience, skill level, educational background, and interview performance, employers decide which applicants are the greatest fit for the position (Indeed Editorial Team, 2021).

Efficiency

Performance is the extent to which goals are met or the possibility for meeting goals in relation to key organizational attributes for the relevant stakeholders (Ghalem, Okar, Chroqui and Alami, 2017). Therefore, a multidimensional collection of criteria is mostly used to specify performance. The acts of participants in business processes are the source of performance. Performance is the accomplishment of a goal by an organization rather than an individual using the least amount of resources possible. Performance is the degree of accomplishment attained by a person, group, company, or process. Effectiveness and efficiency are two concepts that are connected to performance in the performance measurement literature. Effectiveness is an indicator of the degree of goal attainment, while efficiency is an indicator of the resources used to obtain the level of success (Hill, & Thompson, 2019).

Performance of Employees

An employee's performance is evaluated based on how successfully or poorly they carry out their assigned tasks and how quickly they complete deadlines or other criteria. You may uncover potential flaws in your employee training program and get advice on how to fix them by measuring employee performance (Revanth, 2022). Simply said, employee performance refers to how a staff person performs the responsibilities of their employment, completes necessary tasks, and acts in the workplace. The effectiveness, quantity, and quality of work are all considered performance indicators. Leaders may get a picture of how the company is doing when they keep an eye on staff performance. This not only serves to emphasize what businesses can do right now to enhance their operations, but it also provides information for future growth plans.

Employee performance elements utilized to achieve study goals.

Units of Production

This is sometimes referred to as the productive output, production units, or activity units. The term "output" refers to the total amount of products and services produced by a whole nation within a specific time period, or its gross domestic product. The phrase can be used to describe all the labor, effort, commodities, or services that a person, business, factory, or machine produces. It refers to any data that has been processed by and delivered from a computer or other comparable electronic equipment in the field of computing. Everything we see on a computer screen is an output. In economics, output refers to the total amount of products and services produced over a specific time period by an individual, business, industry, city, region, or country, or even the entire planet (Vangie, 2021).

Employee responsiveness

Employee Many of the essential characteristics that constitute contentment and healthy relationships are underpinned by responsiveness. Responding as promptly as you can to a situation is what responsiveness is all about. Example: A consumer mails in a request for particular product details. Now, response may be gauged by how quickly you respond to this email with the required details (Reis, 2018).

Maintenance

The capacity of a business to reduce employee turnover, or the amount of employees who quit their jobs either freely or involuntarily, is known as employee retention. The performance and success of a corporation are directly impacted by staff retention rates. In order to succeed, businesses must retain their top talent. Retention of employees aims to achieve this. Employee retention refers to the tactics a company creates to reduce the likelihood that key employees will leave and the procedures it implements to do so (Marc, 2021). Today, firms and HR departments have a major difficulty in employee retention. People quit their employment for a variety of reasons. Others are forced, like being laid off, while some are choice, like changing jobs. Instead of the loss of a poor performance, employee retention methods largely concentrate on voluntary turnover that is harmful to the company. It also emphasizes turnover that may be prevented, such as when a person quits their job to relocate out-of-state.

Theoretical Foundation

Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory and Two-Factor Theory served as the study's guiding theories. The Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory served as the study's foundation. The notion is in favor of non-financial incentives in that employees are motivated to meet certain needs, either at work or elsewhere. When employees find the flexibility of attending to their personal commitments as they fulfil their career obligations, they get the motivation to pursue the next need inline.

Maslow's Theory of Needs Hierarchy

Their desire to meet demands farther up the hierarchy is what motivates them to work toward and accomplish a certain objective (Armstrong, 2009). Abraham Maslow (1943) distinguished five tiers of requirements that range from basic survival to self-actualization. When the demands at one level are addressed, a newfound motivation to meet the needs at the following level emerges (Gunnigle, Heraty and Morley, 2011). Requirements are placed in a pyramidal order according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Kouloubandi, Jofreh & Mahdavi, 2012). Self-actualization is at the summit of the pyramid, while physiological necessities are at the base. Employees who are focused on satisfying their physical requirements won't have the energy to focus on the needs at the next level of the hierarchy. However, adequate compensation is essential to meeting the lower-level demands of an organization's workforce (Udechukwu, 2009). Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory is pertinent to this study since it supports non-financial incentives by showing that employees tend to meet needs, whether or not those needs are work-related. Employees get motivated to seek the next need in line when they have the freedom to balance taking care of personal duties while fulfilling their professional obligations. Employees are more likely to remain in such a company to ensure that they realize themselves if they can meet these demands while still working there.

Two-Factor Theory

The two-factor theory of workplace motivation was created by Herzberg. The two-factor theory was built on the premise that there are two sets of variables that affect motivation at work by either boosting or detracting from employee happiness. According to this hypothesis, two variables determine an employee's performance and attitude at work. These two elements are motivation and good hygiene (Yuso et al., 2013). According to Yuso et al. (2013), although extrinsic variables (hygiene factors) are

able to keep employees from being dissatisfied, internal elements (motivation factors) increase employees' job satisfaction. According to Robbins (2009), in order to improve performance or effectiveness, employers must consider internal elements like as motivation. Therefore, the motivational components must be important in order to encourage personnel. Organizations should place a strong emphasis on offering intrinsic or motivational aspects since these elements boost employees' effectiveness and productivity (Yusouf et al., 2013).

Empirical Analysis

To determine the degree of employee satisfaction with the incentive system applied by three (3) chosen postsecondary institutions in Enugu State, Nigeria, Ghasi and Onyejiaku (2018). For this investigation, a survey approach was used. 1122 employees from the non-academic personnel at the chosen higher education institutions in Enugu State, Nigeria, made up the study's population. Using Taro Yamane's finite population formula from 1964, a sample size of 415 was determined. After being approved by professionals in academia and human resources management, 415 questionnaires were utilized to gather information from respondents who were non-academic staff members. The proportionate sample size was determined using Burley's proportional allocation. Three hundred and one (301) copies out of the 415 copies distributed—were returned and utilized in the study. Primary and secondary sources were used to get the data. When the instrument's dependability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, an Alpha of 0.79 was achieved, validating the instrument's reliability. Z test was used to evaluate the hypotheses that were developed. According to study results, there was little staff satisfaction with the reward system used by tertiary institutions during the study period (computed z-value of 24.385 against 1.645 and significance of 0.000) ($z = 24.385 >$ at $p 0.05$). The study draws the conclusion that, in the higher education institutions under examination, the incentive system in place has a very significant association with the satisfaction of non-academic employees.

In several selected public universities in the South East of Nigeria, Orajaka (2021) looked at organizational performance and its effects on employee recognition and job satisfaction. The study examined how management success in a few chosen firms in south-eastern Nigeria was rewarded in relation to work satisfaction and employee recognition. To assess the significant association and coefficient of determination of the variables, descriptive statistics, correlation tools, and mean likert were used. However, the tools demonstrate that there is a significant positive link between employee recognition and work satisfaction in public universities. The correlation reveals a significant value of 0.000 and a correlation coefficient of 0.942. This demonstrated that the system had a strong, positive, substantial link. These findings showed that, in the research areas chosen, job satisfaction and employee recognition have a significant beneficial impact on organizational performance.

At the Lake Victoria South Water Services Board in Kisumu, Kenya, Ondhowe, Kadima, and Juma (2021) conducted research on the impact of recognition practices on employee performance. Therefore, the goal of this study was to examine the impact of non-cash rewards on worker performance at Kisumu's Lake Victoria South Water Service Board (LVSWSB). The study specifically aimed to investigate how employee performance in LVSWSB is influenced by recognition. A descriptive research design was used for the study. Census was used as the sampling approach since the population was controllable. The questionnaire served as the data gathering tool. Utilizing computer tools, descriptive and inferential analytical statistics were produced (SPSS version 24). According to the results of the Chi-square test, employee performance is influenced by recognition. In conclusion, employee performance is directly impacted by recognition.

Agbenyegah (2019) identifies the role of monetary and non-monetary incentives in enhancing employee performance in Ghanaian financial institutions. This study employed an exploratory technique with qualitative methodology. Researchers discovered that both monetary and non-monetary rewards had an impact on employee performance. They advise organizations to increase employee productivity by increasing salaries, allowances, retirement benefits, leave benefits, and programs for affordable housing. They also recommend that organizations teach different employee types to enhance and grow their conceptual, interpersonal, and technical abilities.

The role of employees' responsiveness in organizational performance was the subject of a 2018 study by Vivi, Sitti, Marta, and Erwin. Through employee responsiveness as an intermediary variable, the study sought to ascertain the extent to which the leadership style and innovation of the leader had an impact on organizational performance. Leadership Style (X1), Leader's Innovation (X2), Employee Responsiveness (Z), and Organizational Performance are the research variables (Y). 48 respondents were given surveys and questionnaires as part of the methods used to obtain the data. The validity and reliability test, correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, path analysis, and t-test were all employed as data analysis techniques. The findings indicate that Leadership Style had a positive and significant impact on organizational performance, Leader's Innovation had a negative and significant impact on organizational performance, Employee's Responsiveness had a positive but not significant impact on organizational performance, and Leadership Style had a negative but not significant impact on Employee's Responsiveness.

In their study of the association between supervisor support, job satisfaction, and life happiness among female nurses in China, Oscar, Chen, Bamini, Balakrishnan, & Michelle (2021) looked at the mediating effect of flexible working hours. Using online survey questionnaires, a cross-sectional quantitative study was carried out. 2019 saw the implementation of convenience sampling with 171 female nurses from two tertiary public hospitals. According to the mediation analysis, flexible working hours significantly and favorably mediate the relationship between job satisfaction and supervisor support ($r = 0.775$, $p.001$) and life satisfaction ($r = 0.745$, $p.001$). Additionally, flexible work schedules and supervisor support have a positive and significant impact on job ($r = 0.520$, $p .01$; $r = 0.520$, $p .01$) and life satisfaction ($r = 0.487$, $p .01$; $r = 0.487$, $p .01$). According to the study, flexible working hours might help nurses feel more satisfied with their jobs and with their lives ($r = 0.656$, $p .01$). The study found that for female nurses who have demanding schedules at work and at home, flexible working hours and supervisor assistance are essential.

With organizational commitment as an intervening variable, Andi & Syihabudhin (2018) investigated the Influence of Reward on Turnover Intention (A Study on Group I and II Employee at Djatiroto Sugar Factory). The purpose of the study was to ascertain the relationship between organizational commitment, turnover intention, and incentive variables, as well as how these factors affected the workers at the Djatioroto Sugar Factory in Lumajang. 217 of the 472 employees of Group I and II of the Djatioroto Sugar Factory in Lumajang participated in the study by utilizing the proportionate random sample method. Using path analysis, the findings revealed a significant direct relationship between rewards and turnover intention as well as between rewards and organizational commitment and turnover intention itself. Additionally, organizational commitment acts as an intermediary variable in the indirect relationship between rewards and turnover intention.

A study on rewards and work engagement of non-academic staff was conducted by Abeera, Augustina, and John (2020) using the example of a public university in Uganda. In a public university in Uganda, the study looked at the impact of employee awards on nonacademic staff members' commitment to their

jobs. The study specifically looked at the link between support staff members' work engagement and intrinsic and extrinsic rewards. The study used a quantitative strategy and a correlational research methodology. A questionnaire survey was used to get the data. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used in data analysis. Means were used in descriptive statistics, whereas correlation and regression analysis were used in inferential statistics. According to the descriptive findings, while respondents gave intrinsic rewards, vigor, and devotion high ratings, they gave absorption and extrinsic incentives a middling rating. According to inferential analysis, work engagement was positively and significantly correlated with both intrinsic and extrinsic incentives. It was determined that intrinsic and extrinsic rewards are crucial for enhancing employees' motivation at work.

In order to determine the extent to which organizational reward systems have an effect on employee retention in the banking sector in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, Amadi, Zeb-Obipi, Lebura, and Poi (2021) conducted research. The link between compensation, promotion, and recognition—three components of incentive systems—and employee retention has been investigated in this study in order to meet this goal. The survey study design was employed in terms of technique, and the structured questionnaire was the main tool for gathering data. Descriptive and inferential statistics, as well as the spearman's test statistics, were used to examine the obtained data. The findings showed that compensation, promotion, and recognition as elements of incentive systems and employee retention have a favorable association. The conclusion reached is that banks in Port Harcourt would need to enhance their incentive systems, especially the compensation, promotion, and recognition that they provide to their workers, in order to retain their finest personnel.

Methodology

The study was based on the six (6) selected private hospitals in Enugu state. The hospitals were: Annunciation Specialist Hospital, 27, Annunciation Hospital Road, Emene; POsH Hospital, 100 Chime Avenue, New Haven; St. Patrick Specialist Hospital and Maternity, 8, Owerri Road, Asata; Memfys Hospital for Neurosurgery, Plot 13 Trans-Ekulu Pocket Layout, Km 2 Enugu-Onitsha Expressway, Niger Foundation Hospital, 5 Presidential Close, Enugu and Balm of Gilead Specialist Hospital, Maryland, 12 Prince Okam Street. These organizations were chosen for high number of staff, over 40 million naira capital based and high ethical standard. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of six hundred and eighty-three (683), staff was used. The sample size of 246, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. 242 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.77 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to test the hypotheses (r).

Data presentation and analyses

4.1 The relationship between recognition and the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State.

Table 4.1.1: Responses on the relationship between recognition and the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	∑FX	-	SD	Decisio
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		n
1	The employees build a service of security in their value to the hospital and it motivate them to be productivity	600 120 49.6	296 74 30.6	36 12 5.0	20 10 4.1	26 26 10.7	978 242 100%	4.04	1.297	Agree
2	The employee contributions to the success of their team are noted and acknowledge which promotes handwork .	735 147 60.7	112 28 11.6	18 6 2.5	52 26 10.7	35 35 14.5	952 242 100%	3.93	1.539	Agree
3	The employees are connected to their work when appreciated and recognized	465 93 38.4	328 82 33.9	18 6 2.5	52 26 10.7	35 35 14.5	898 242 100%	3.71	1.437	Agree
4	Team culture is encouraged and improved when good work is recognized.	745 149 61.6	56 28 11.6	18 6 2.5	52 26 10.7	33 33 13.6	904 242 100%	3.97	1.519	Agree
5	There is increased retention of quality employees in the organization as quality service in occufnned	300 60 24.8	504 126 53.3	18 6 2.5	52 26 10.7	21 21 8.7	895 242 100%	3.75	1.194	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.88	1.397	2

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 4.1.1, 194 respondents out of 242 representing 80.2 percent agreed that the employees build a service of security in their value to the hospital and it motivate them to be productivity 4.04 and standard deviation of 1.297. The employee contributions to the success of their team are noted and acknowledge which promotes handwork 175 respondents representing 72.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.93 and standard deviation of 1.539. The employees are connected to their work when appreciated and recognized. 175 respondents representing 72.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.71 and standard deviation of 1.519. Team culture is encouraged and improved when good work is recognized. 177 respondents representing 73.2 percent agreed with mean score of 3.97 and 1.519. There is increased retention of quality employees in the organization as quality service in occuned 186 respondents representing 78.1 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.75 and standard deviation 1.194.

The relationship between flexible working hours and employee responsiveness of private hospitals in Enugu State

Table 4.2.1: Responses on the relationship between flexible working hours and employee responsiveness of private hospitals in Enugu State

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 D A	1 SD	∑FX	- X	SD	Decisio n
1	Flexible working hours increase employee loyalty.	440 88 36.4	404 101 41.7	18 6 2.5	52 26 10. 7	21 21 8.7	935 242 100%	3.86	1.260	Agree
2	The promotes of employee engagement is enhanced by flexible hours in the workplace.	430 86 35.5	412 103 42.6	18 6 2.5	26 26 10. 7	21 21 8.7	907 242 100%	3.86	1.256	Agree
3	Remote workers actually save organization’s money	395 79 32.6	440 110 45.5	18 6 2.5	26 26 10. 7	21 21 8.7	900 242 100%	3.83	1.240	Agree
4	Less employee turnover is enhanced as flexible hours increases job satisfaction.	250 50 20.7	600 150 62.0	18 6 2.5	20 10 4.1	26 26 10.7	914 242 100%	3.78	1.149	Agree
5	The wiliness and ability to readily respond to changing circumstances boost employee morals.	360 72 29.8	440 110 45.5	18 6 2.5	20 10 4.1	44 44 18.2	1209 242 100%	3.64	1.416	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.79	1.265	4

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 4.2.1, 189 respondents out of 242 representing 78.1 percent agreed that flexible working hours increase employee loyalty 3.86 and standard deviation of 1.260. The promotes of employee engagement is enhanced by flexible hours in the workplace 189 respondents representing 78.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.86 and standard deviation of 1.256. Remote workers actually save organization’s money. 189 respondents representing 78.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.83 and standard deviation of 1.240. Less employee turnover is enhanced as flexible hours increases job satisfaction. 200 respondents representing 82.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.78 and 1.149. The wiliness and ability to readily respond to changing circumstances boost employee morals 182 respondents representing 75.3 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.64 and standard deviation 1.416.

The relationship between employee with more responsibility and retention of private hospitals in Enugu state

Table 4.3.1: Responses on the relationship between employee with more responsibility and retention of private hospitals in Enugu state

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decisio
		SA	A	N	D	SD		X		n
					A					
1	Exposing employees to career opportunity motivates them to keep their job.	715 143 59.1	228 57 23.6	18 6 2.5	20 10 4.1	26 26 10.7	1162 242 100%	4.16	1.315	Agree
2	There is next level of the employee career with more responsibility	310 62 25.6	552 138 57.0	18 6 2.5	20 10 4.1	26 26 10.7	926 242 100%	3.83	1.178	Agree
3	Employees with more responsibility build professional bonds with coworkers.	320 64 26.4	592 148 61.2	6 6 2.5	20 10 4.1	14 14 5.8	952 242 100%	3.98	.989	Agree
4	The employee value and leadership to the organization is sustained.	785 157 64.9	220 55 22.7	18 3 1.2	26 13 5.4	14 14 5.8	1063 242 100%	4.36	1.129	Agree
5	The increased responsibilities bring faster learning and growth.	685 137 56.6	244 61 25.2	18 6 2.5	48 24 9.9	14 14 5.8	1009 242 100%	4.17	1.219	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.1	1.166	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 4.3.1, 200 respondents out of 242 representing 82.7 percent agreed that exposing employees to career opportunity motivates them to keep their job 4.16 and standard deviation of 1.315. There is next level of the employee career with more responsibility 200 respondents representing 82.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.98 and standard deviation of 1.178. Employees with more responsibility build professional bonds with coworkers. 212 respondents representing 87.6 percent agreed with mean score of 3.98 and standard deviation of .999. The employee value and leadership to the organization is sustained. 212 respondents representing 87.6 percent agreed with mean score of 4.36 and 1.129. The increased responsibilities bring faster learning and growth 198 respondents representing 81.8 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.17 and standard deviation 1.219.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Recognition has no positive significant relationship with the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State.

Correlations

	The employees build a service of security in their value to the hospital and it motivate them to be productivity	The employee contributions to the success of their team are noted and acknowledge which promotes hardwork.	The employees are connected to their work when appreciated and recognized	Team culture is encouraged and improved when good work is recognized.	There is increased retention of quality employees in the organization as quality service in occurred
The employees build a service of security in their value to the hospital and it motivate them to be productivity	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 242	.384** .000 242	.391** .000 242	.224** .000 242	.226** .000 242
The employee contributions to the success of their team are noted and acknowledge which promotes hard work.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 242	1 .000 242	.763** .000 242	.722** .000 242	.652** .000 242
The employees are connected to their work when appreciated and recognized	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 242	.391** .000 242	1 .000 242	.716** .000 242	.603** .000 242
Team culture is encouraged and improved when good work is recognized.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 242	.224** .000 242	.722** .000 242	1 .000 242	.702** .000 242
There is increased retention of quality employees in the organization as quality service in occurred	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N 242	.226** .000 242	.652** .000 242	.603** .000 242	1 .000 242

Table 4.4.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on recognition and the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .224 < .762. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05

level (2 tailed) and implies that recognition had positive significant relationship with the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State.

($r = .224 < .762$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .224 < .762$, $p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .224 < .762$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that recognition had positive significant relationship with the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .224 < .762$., $p < .05$).

Hypothesis Two: Flexible working hours has no positive significant relationship with employee responsiveness of private hospitals in Enugu State.

Correlations

		Flexible working hours increase employee loyalty.	The promotes of employee engagement is enhanced by flexible hours in the workplace.	Remote workers actually save organization's money	Less employee turnover is enhanced as flexible hours increases job satisfaction.	The wiliness and ability to readily respond to changing circumstances boost employee morals.
Flexible working hours increase employee loyalty.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .000 242	.740** .000 242	.784** .000 242	.779** .000 242	.691** .000 242
The promotes of employee engagement is enhanced by flexible hours in the workplace.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.740** .000 242	1 .000 242	.797** .000 242	.711** .000 242	.734** .000 242
Remote workers actually save organization's money	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.784** .000 242	.797** .000 242	1 .000 242	.736** .000 242	.468** .000 242
Less employee turnover is enhanced as flexible hours increases job satisfaction.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.779** .000 242	.711** .000 242	.736** .000 242	1 .000 242	.660** .000 242
The wiliness and ability to readily respond to changing circumstances boost employee morals.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.691** .000 242	.734** .000 242	.468** .000 242	.660** .000 242	1 .000 242

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.4.2.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on Flexible working hours and employee responsiveness showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .468 < .797. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level

(2 tailed) and implies that Flexible working hours had positive significant relationship with employee responsiveness of private hospitals in Enugu State ($r=.468 <.797$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r=.468 <.797$, $p <.05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r =.468 <.797$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that Flexible working hours had positive significant relationship with employee responsiveness of private hospitals in Enugu State as reported in the probability value of ($r=.468 <.797$., $p <.05$).

Hypothesis Three: Employee with more responsibility has no positive significant relationship with retention of private hospitals in Enugu State.

Correlations

		Exposing employees to career opportunity motivates them to keep their job.	There is next level of the employee career with more responsibility	Employees with more responsibility build professional bonds with coworkers.	The employee value and leadership to the organization is sustained.	The increased responsibilities bring faster learning and growth.
Exposing employees to career opportunity motivates them to keep their job.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .878** 242	.878** .000 242	.519** .000 242	.436** .000 242	.490** .000 242
There is next level of the employee career with more responsibility	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.878** .000 242	1 .000 242	.556** .000 242	.374** .000 242	.601** .000 242
Employees with more responsibility build professional bonds with coworkers.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.519** .000 242	.556** .000 242	1 .000 242	.662** .000 242	.608** .000 242
The employee value and leadership to the organization is sustained.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.436** .000 242	.374** .000 242	.662** .000 242	1 .000 242	.538** .000 242
The increased responsibilities bring faster learning and growth.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.490** .000 242	.601** .000 242	.608** .000 242	.538** .000 242	1 .000 242

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.4.3.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on employee with more responsibility and retention showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .374 < .878. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that employee with more responsibility had positive significant relationship with

retention of private hospitals in Enugu State ($r = .374 < .878$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .374 < .878, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .374 < .878$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that employee with more responsibility had positive significant relationship with retention of private hospitals in Enugu State as reported in the probability value of ($r = .374 < .878, p < .05$).

Summary of Findings

- i. Recognition had positive significant relationship with the units of output of private hospitals in Enugu State, ($r = .224 < .762$).
- ii. Flexible working hours had positive significant relationship with employee responsiveness of private hospitals in Enugu State, ($r = .468 < .797$).
- iii. Employee with more responsibility had positive significant relationship with retention of private hospitals in Enugu State, ($r = .374 < .878$).

Conclusion

The study found a substantial beneficial association between recognition, flexible working hours, and employees with greater responsibility and the production units, staff response, and retention of private hospitals in Enugu State. On the other side, motivated personnel are more likely to be tenacious, creative, and competent. Employee retention, loyalty, and cohesion are at their highest levels when motivated staff members are happy, committed, and enthusiastic about their job. These elements considerably aid in the expansion and improvement of the entire business.

Recommendations

- i. The hospital management should view recognition as a means of showing workers that the company values their work and the contributions they make to the success of both their teams and the organization as a whole.
- ii. In order to boost employee morale and improve their physical and emotional well-being, it is essential that the organization's management offer flexible working hours. Stress and burnout will be decreased.
- iii. The management should work to empower the staff in order to win their loyalty and contentment in order for them to make better crucial business judgments.

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